
Handbook and guidance material for the implementation of the MOBAK App

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Technical sheet

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1. Introduction

This handbook is intended to assist users of the MOBAK App (Lüthy et al., 2023) in how to use the app and what to look out for when using it.

Figure 1: Icon Mobak app

1.1 What the MOBAK app is about

The MOBAK App can basically be used for two scenarios. On the one hand, the app can be used to diagnose basic motor competencies of primary school children. On the other hand, the app provides a wide range of learning tasks to support teachers in planning lessons that promote basic motor competencies. Later on, you will find out how you can use the two functions of the app together (cf. 3.1 & 3.2).

2. Using the app for diagnostics

2.1 Diagnostic tasks

The diagnostic tasks in the app contain the MOBAK test tasks and are divided into two levels, MOBAK 1-2 and MOBAK 3-4. They can be used to determine the level of children's basic motor competencies, the effectiveness of physical education, the need of support, to describe developmental trajectory or to evaluate interventions in physical education.

For use in the classroom, it is important to note that, depending on the teacher's intentions, only one competence area (self-movement/object movement) or individual basic motor competencies can be diagnosed. More information: Test manual (Herrmann, 2018).

Figure 2: Discover test tasks

Figure 3: Test tasks choose grade level

Figure 4: Details test task balancing

2.2 Create Class

Before you can use the MOBAK app for diagnostics and do the MOBAK test with your class, you need to create your class and add students.

1. Click on the house icon in the bottom right corner (see Fig. 5).
2. Click *New Class* to add your class (see Fig. 6).
3. Enter the name of the class and select the grade (see Fig. 7).
4. Click on Add new class to save the entries.
5. Click on the class you have just created and click on “Add student”. Add students one at a time, enter the names of all your students and select their gender (see Fig. 8-11).

Figure 5: House icon for the test area

Figure 6: New class

Figure 7: Enter name

Figure 8: Choose grade

Figure 9: Choose class

Figure 10: Add student

Figure 11: Name and gender

2.3 Test assessment

You can find all the information about the test tasks in the app. When you are on the home screen, click on “Let’s start!” (see Fig. 2). Now you can select the age group (MOBAK 1-2 or MOBAK 3-4) at the top of the app and below you will find all the test tasks divided into the competence areas of object movement and self-movement (see Fig. 3). If you click on one of the test tasks, all the information the test leader needs to carry out the test is listed. (see Fig. 4, 12).

Figure 12: Rating view

To perform the test, follow the steps below:

1. Select the class you wish to take the test with (you can find your classes by clicking on the house icon on the home screen) (see Fig. 5).
2. Click on “Test class”. Complete the test tasks with the students, score the students and click on the correct test result. Please note that the selected results for each test task are automatically saved (see Fig. 13).
3. End the test when you have entered all the students’ results “End test session” (see Fig. 14).

Figure 13: Entering the student's assessment

Figure 14: End test session

2.4 Test evaluation

Afterwards you can export a PDF file with the test results. To export the PDF, you click on the house icon at the home screen and then select a class (see Fig. 5). Then select a completed test (see Fig. 15). There you can see the average test scores for the competence areas “self-movement” and “object movement” within the app. You can also see the results for each individual student (see Fig. 17).

Figure 15: Select test evaluation

Figure 16: View evaluation

Figure 17: Individual results

Clicking on *Export test information* (see Fig. 18) will generate a PDF file. There you can see the results of all students, both at the level of basic motor qualifications and at the level of basic motor competencies. You can also see the class average for each of the basic motor qualifications and for the two competence areas (see Fig. 19-20).

When students score 7 or 8 points in one competence area, the results are marked in green. This means that they are better than the average. If students score 0 to 2 points in a competence area, the test results are marked in red. This means that they need support.

Figure 18: Generate PDF file

Date : 18-01-2024 09:29
Class : Handbook

St	Na	Sex	Self movement	Object movement	Self movement	Object movement	Rolling	Jumping	Running	Bouncing	Catching	Throwing	Dribbling
01	Student 1	M	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
02	Student 2	M	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
03	Student 3	M	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
04	Student 4	M	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
05	Student 5	M	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
06	Student 6	M	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
07	Student 7	M	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Class average			1.2	1.3	1.2	1.3	1.2	1.3	1.2	1.3	1.2	1.3	1.2

Procedure for the selection of learning tasks for support:

- Compare the class average of the total value self movement and object movement (interlaces of the row and columns highlighted in gray).
 - Select the range with the lower value.
- Compare the class averages of the MOBAC competencies (Balancing, rolling, jumping, running or throwing, catching, bouncing, dribbling) (gray line).
 - Select the competencies with the class average below 1 (gray line).
 - If the class average is not less than 1 for any competency, choose the one with the lowest score.
- Compare the distribution of the class (rows below the gray line).
 - Choose the competency in which the majority of children have performed the weakest.
 - Choose the learning tasks that match this competency.

Figure 19: PDF file

Id	Sex	Name	Balancing	Rolling	Jumping	Running	Total self movement	Bouncing	Catching	Throwing	Dribbling	Total object movement
#1	F	Student	1	1	1	1	4	1	2	1	0	4
#2	F	Student	2	1	2	1	6	2	2	2	1	7
#3	F	Student	2	2	1	1	6	2	2	2	0	6
#4	M	Student	1	2	1	0	4	1	2	0	1	4
#5	M	Student	1	1	2	1	5	0	2	2	0	4
#6	M	Student	n/a	0	2	1	n/a	1	1	2	1	5
#7	D	Student	1	0	1	2	4	2	2	1	0	5
#8	D	Student	2	1	0	1	4	1	2	2	1	6
#9	D	Student	2	1	0	1	4	1	1	2	0	4
		Class average	1.50	1.00	1.11	1.00	4.63	1.22	1.78	1.56	0.44	5.00
		0(%)	0%	22%	22%	11%	0%	11%	0%	11%	56%	0%
		1(%)	50%	56%	44%	78%	100%	56%	22%	22%	44%	89%
		2(%)	50%	22%	33%	11%	0%	33%	78%	67%	0%	11%
		Total (N)	8	9	9	9	8	9	9	9	9	9

Figure 20: Table of test evaluation

The PDF includes the following reading guide to help you interpret the results:

- Procedure for selecting learning tasks for support: Compare the class average of the “self-movement” and “object movement” total scores (intersection of the grey highlighted row and column):
 - Select the area with the lower value.
- Compare the class averages of the MOBAK competencies (balancing, rolling, jumping, running or throwing, catching, bouncing, dribbling - grey line):
 - Select the competencies for which the class average is less than 1 (grey line).
 - If the class average is not less than 1 for any competence, select the one with the lowest score.
- Compare the distribution of the class (area below the grey line)
 - Select the competence in which the majority of children performed the worst.
 - Choose the learning tasks that correspond to this competence.

It is possible to carry out and analyse individual test tasks. However, you will only get the most comprehensive test evaluation if you do all the test items, or at least all the test items in one competence area.

3. Using the app for planning

The planning of physical activity and physical education lessons can be approached in different ways, either through the diagnosis at the beginning or as a conclusion. It is also possible to make the diagnosis at the beginning and at the end, so that a possible learning progress of the students becomes visible.

3.1 From diagnosis to learning tasks

The initial diagnosis can be used to determine the student's current level of ability. Based on the generated PDF file, it is possible to see which competence area (e.g. "self-movement") and, more specifically, which basic motor qualification (e.g. "rolling") is most in need of support in the class.

Based on the results, the learning tasks for the class are now selected and carried out.

Regarding individual support, learning tasks can also be selected from different basic motor qualifications. For this purpose, the test results of the individual students are examined in more detail.

3.2 From learning task to diagnosis

The numerous learning tasks can also be used without prior diagnosis. To do this, the teacher selects the tasks that he or she considers appropriate for the class. Again, the focus is on improving motor qualifications or competencies. After carrying out the learning tasks over several lessons, a diagnosis is made at the end to check the effectiveness of the lessons.

3.3 Learning Tasks

The use of the learning tasks depends on how they are prepared by the teacher. The tasks are suitable for an introduction or the main part of a lesson. The learning tasks in the competence area "self-movement" can be done individually or in tandems. In the competence area "object movement", there are also tasks that can be done with the whole class.

Individual or tandem tasks are suitable for station work or, with minor adjustments, for working in the whole class. To do justice to the heterogeneity, it is a good idea to carry out the learning tasks in different variations. Here, there is no division into levels of difficulty, but the children should decide for themselves what is easy for them and what is still difficult. This can be done by adding material, changing the direction or complexity of the movement. The students' own ideas can also be taken into account, which is encouraged by the reflection questions. These even serve to increase motor competence, as the focus is not only on ability, but also on the areas of knowledge, understanding and willingness and are a central part of the learning tasks.

The reflection questions can be posed to the class as a whole or to the children individually during the learning process. In addition to the reflection questions specifically developed for the tasks listed in the app, it is also possible to ask the questions below, which are suitable for all learning tasks.

Knowledge and Understanding

I succeed at...

- thumb feedback
- telling (good, great, not at all, ...)
- show with fingers (1-5)

What have you already achieved?

What have you not achieved yet?

What can you do to be more successful in this task?

- Change your movement.
- Change the material.

How did you manage to complete the task successfully? How did you do it?

- Show me your best solution.
- Explain and justify your solution to me.

How will the task change for you if you... (refer to variations)?

Willingness

What do you like about this task?

What don't you like about this task?

How could you make the task more difficult for you? Would you like to try it?

How could you make the task more enjoyable for you?

Show your solution to another child. Try his or her solution as well.

Which solution is easier for you?

Which solution do you like better?

3.4 Learning tasks in the MOBAK app

The start page offers the possibility to choose between the two competence areas “self-movement” (see Fig.21) and “object movement” (see Fig. 22).

Figure 21: Learning tasks "self-movement"

Figure 22: Learning tasks "object movement"

The basic motor qualification is then selected by clicking on the arrow on the right.

The example of running is used to show how the learning tasks can be accessed (see Fig. 21 - 27).

Figure 23: Overview running

Figure 24: Learning task Running 1

The individual categories can be accessed by clicking on the arrows on the right-hand side (see Fig. 25).

Figure 25: Category selection

The variations opened on a separate page and can be viewed individually or as a whole (see Fig. 26).

Each category can be accessed by clicking on the arrows on the right-hand side (see Fig. 27).

Figure 26: View Skills variation

Figure 27: Selection Skills variation

To add a learning task to your favorites, click on the heart icon in the top right-hand corner of the task itself. Tasks saved to favorites can be easily found using the bar below the home screen (see Fig. 29 - 30).

Figure 28: Add as favourite

Figure 29: Find favourites

Figure 30: View favourites

4. Practical examples

Below are four different practical examples in which a possible use of the learning tasks in the classroom is shown. The first two are intended as a teaching sequence, the other two as an individualised way of working.

4.1 Dribbling Lesson Sequence

In this sequence, the learning tasks “Protecting young fish” and “Within shark territory” are combined into a story, in which the children first protect and transport the young fish as a group, and then each child individually leads a young fish through the shark's territory.

4.1.1 Protecting young fish

Five children form a circle and hold each other by the hands. Their balls (=young fish) are situated in the middle on the floor. The group's task is to "carry" their young fish to a certain place (e.g., cones) with their feet and without losing any of them.

Instructions from the teacher:

"You form a circle, and you hold each other's hands. In the middle you have a young fish (ball), which you take together to the other shore (hall side). You are only allowed to touch the young fish with your feet."

Reflection:

What changes when you dribble the ball together compared to dribbling the ball alone?

What do you pay attention to when you dribble the ball in a group?

As a group, can you move several balls at the same time?

"How many young fishes (different balls) can you accompany at the same time?"

Reflection:

How can you help each other in the group?

"Which group can swim the fastest with the young fish to the other side?"

Reflection:

Do you prefer doing the task with or without competing against others and why?

4.1.2 Within shark territory

The children try to enter the "territory of the shark" (area separated by ropes where one "shark" child is located). Every child leads the ball with their feet. Who can dribble through the territory without being caught by the "shark"?

Instructions from the teacher:

"As a group, you have protected the young fish very well. Now, however, all young fish must be guided through the shark's territory. To attract as little attention as possible, you go alone. Take different little fishes."

Reflection

What's the best way to get to the other side without getting caught by the shark? (show some examples and have them imitated)

What's the best way to dribble when you're also looking at the shark?

As a shark, how do you manage to grab a child's ball and keep dribbling?

How do you go about avoiding getting caught?

How do you go about not getting caught?

When do you think the shark should be replaced and why?

Which young fish can you best accompany?

“Will you be able to get the young fishes through the shark's territory?”

Reflection:

What's the best way to do it?

How do you go about not getting caught?

How does the task change for you when you accompany a young fish in pairs?

4.2 Lesson Sequence Jumping

In this lesson sequence, the learning tasks “Ground rope Jumping 1” and “Ground rope Jumping 2” are combined. The task becomes more complex and the children can vary the level of difficulty themselves.

4.2.1 Ground rope Jumping 1

The children stand parallel to the rope and jump over it several times.

“Three students go together. Stand parallel to the rope and jump over the rope several times.”

Reflection

How do you change the movement when you jump sideways or back and forth?

“How can you still jump over the rope? Invent tricks that you can repeat several times.”

Reflection

Can you do tricks when you jump? Show and teach it to another child.

“Two children hold the rope and lift it off the ground. You can change the height while jumping.”

Reflection

Do you jump differently when the rope is raised?

What is the highest height you can jump? Challenge yourself!

“Two children hold the rope and swing it so that it touches the ground.”

Reflection

Do you jump differently when the rope swings?

What's the best way to jump in time?

4.2.2 Ground rope Jumping 2

Two ropes create a cross and in each field there is a number (e.g., the field at the top left is no. 1).

The children stand with their left leg in one of the squares and, when called a number, jump into the corresponding square and land there on their right leg. For the next number, the landing is made with the left foot, and so on.

“Now take two ropes and lay them in a cross on the floor. Place a number from 1 to 4 in each square. One child stands with his left foot in a square. The other child calls out a number from 1 to 4. The child in the cross now jumps with his or her right leg into the corresponding square and when the next number is called he or she jumps with the left leg into the next corresponding square, and so on.” (Note: be sure to show it)

Reflection

What do you do to respond quickly to the shouting?

How can you, as a shouter, make the task easier or more difficult for the child?

Get together in pairs. Think up a high-five ritual that you perform when one of you makes it through 10 attempts without a mistake. How do you feel if you get a high-five?

“Agree on a sequence of numbers together. The calling child is allowed to change the speed of the calling.”

Reflection

What changes when you know the order of the numbers being called, compared to not knowing which number comes next?

“Try different variations when jumping.”

Reflection:

Is it easier to jump with one or both legs? Why?

4.3 Individual work in jumping

The basic tasks of the following learning tasks are shown to the children or, depending on the class, introduced in more detail. Each child is given a jump rope and a jump pass. The children work independently on the tasks, either individually or in tandems. They record their ideas and self-assessment in the jump pass. The children work with the help of the post-sheets or higher level reflection questions or without help. This is adapted to the level of the class. The independent work of the students gives the teacher time for individual support.

The jump passes can be used by the teacher as a guide to the children's learning level.

4.4 Individual work in balancing

The balancing pass is very similar to the jump pass. Due to the pictures, however, an introduction is not absolutely necessary.

References

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Appendix

In the appendix you will find the material for the jump pass and the balancing pass to print out.

Jump Pass of: _____

		This is how I succeed in the task	My Idea
	Rope Skipping 1 Run forward with the rope and jump over the rope every second step!		
	Rope Skipping 2 Run through the coordination ladder with one rope and one ground contact per field!		
	Rope Skipping 3 Jump with the rope on both legs!		
	Rope Skipping 4 Jump the rope in place with one leg.		

Rope Skipping 1

Run forward with the rope and jump over the rope every second step!

Variations

Jump over the rope with every step.

Vary the running speed.

Vary the number of steps after which you jump over the rope.

Run and jump backwards through the rope.

Perform a slalom race (e.g., with marking cones).

Walk forward and jump over an object every second step.

Rope Skipping 2

Run through the coordination ladder with one rope and one ground contact per field!

Variations

Run backwards.

Run with two ground contacts per field.

Run as fast as possible.

Perform different forms of jumping.

Arrange the fields differently.

Rope Skipping 3

Jump on the rope with both legs!

Variations

Jump with or without intermediate jump.

Swing the rope backwards.

Jump with the rope and move forward and backward (or left and right) across a given line.

Perform squats while jumping rope.

Heel your legs up while jumping.

Pull your knees up when jumping.

Jump on a thin mat.

Rope Skipping 4

Jump the rope in place with one leg.

Variations

Jump with or without intermediate jump.

Jump with the other leg.

Swing the rope backwards.

Switch legs after every other swing ("jump in place").

Jump without rope.

Knowledge and Understanding

I succeed at...

- thumb feedback
- telling (good, great, not at all, ...)
- showing fingers (1-5)

What have you already achieved?

What have you not achieved yet?

What can you do to become more successful in this task?

- Change your movement.
- Change the material.

How did you manage to complete the task successfully? How did you achieve that?

- Show me your best solution.
- Explain and justify your solution to me.

How will the task change for you if you... (relate to variations)?

- ...

Willingness

What do you like about this task?

What don't you like about this task?

How could you make the task more difficult for you? Would you like to try it?

How could you make the task more enjoyable for you?

Show your solution to another child. Try his or her solution as well.

Which solution is easier for you?

Which solution do you like more?

Balancing Pass of: _____

			This is how I succeed in the task	My idea
	<p>Rope balance Balance on the rope that lies flat on the floor.</p>			
	<p>Bench Balancing Balance forward over the narrow side of a bench.</p>			
	<p>Wobbly bench Balance over the narrow side of the bench, which stands on gymnastic bars.</p>			
	<p>Balancing on balls Balance over the medicine balls without touching the ground.</p>			

Rope balance

Balance on the rope that lies flat on the floor.

Variations

Balance backwards.

Balance with your eyes closed.

Throw additional cloths in the air and catch them.

Rotate additional (1 or 2) hoops with your arms.

Choose other material to balance on (e.g., hoops, floor tiles, lines).

Choose other material to balance on a body part (e.g., scarves, hats, balls).

Reflection

What changes when you balance backwards instead of forwards?

Why is balancing easier when you look forward (instead of on the ground, for example)?

Imagine you are tightrope walkers in a circus. How can you balance over the rope together? Can you hear the applause?

How can you put the rope down to make balancing more difficult?

Why it might be important to be able to balance?

Bench balancing

Balance forward over the narrow side of a long bench.

Variations

Change the way you move (sideways, backwards, on all fours).

Perform additional arm movements.

Choose material that you can additionally balance on a part of your body (e.g., scarves, hats, balls).

In addition, place obstacles (e.g., cones) on the bench that you have to cross.

Reflection

What is the best way to put your feet on the bench to balance successfully?

How does your balancing change when you look upwards or downwards instead of forwards?

How does it feel to successfully balance over the bench?

Observe a child who has difficulties balancing over the bench and try to give him/her tips!

Where can you balance other than on the bench to make the task more difficult for you?

Wobbly bench

Balance over the narrow side of the bench, which is placed on gymnastic bars.

Variations

Perform the task without other children, by fixing the long bench on the gymnastics bars with gymnastics mats on all sides so that it does not move.

Walk sideways or backwards.

Put additional obstacles (e.g., cloths, hats) on the bench, and then step over these obstacles.

Add a rotation.

Choose materials that you can additionally balance on a part of your body (e.g., cloths, hats, balls).

Reflection

How do you move to balance on the wobbly bench?

Which arm position helps you most when you balance?

How does it feel to balance over the wobbly bench? Do you need a lot of courage?

Ask the other children to move the bench more slowly/faster depending on how safe you feel.

Balancing on balls

Balance over the medicine balls without touching the ground.

Variations

Walk backwards over the medicine balls.

Use physio/pezzi balls instead of medicine balls.

Cross the medicine balls on all fours.

Let another child help you (if needed). They offer their hand, and you grab it when necessary.

Walk towards each other in pairs and try to pass each other.

Balance with your eyes closed.

Arrange the medicine balls in a different way.

Reflection

What do you do differently when balancing over the balls than when balancing over a bench?

What is the best way to put your feet on the balls to balance successfully?

How do you manage to balance over the balls with your eyes closed?

What objects could be used instead of the medicine balls?

How does it feel to have the balls further apart?

How does it feel to balance over the balls with your eyes closed?